

SkincAlr

Guidelines

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Brand Strategy

Vision

SkincAlr SkincAlr envisions a world where early detection of skin-related Neglected Tropical Diseases (NTDs) is accessible, accurate, and ethically powered by artificial intelligence.

By equipping frontline health workers with inclusive, context-aware technology, we strive to improve health equity in underserved communities across Sub-Saharan Africa.

Mission

SkincAlr's mission is to develop and scale an AI-powered mobile application that enhances the diagnostic capabilities of Front-line Health Workers (FHWs), supports real-time epidemiological surveillance, and fosters inclusive digital health innovation. SkincAlr aims to build the largest open-access dataset of skin NTDs, driving early intervention, improved care, and informed health policy across five countries in Sub-Saharan Africa.

Why define personas?

Defining personas helps us understand the people who use, implement, and are impacted by SkincAlr. From field health workers to national policymakers, each plays a vital role in ensuring the tool is accessible, respectful, and effective.

These profiles shape how we communicate, train, and design—ensuring our message aligns with users' realities and the project's global health mission.

Target

Audience

Aïssatou

Age: 34

Location: Dakar, Senegal

Background: Community health worker in a peri-urban district. Has experience supporting patients with chronic and infectious diseases.

Motivations: Wants to offer accurate and early diagnosis for patients in her area, reducing stigma and long-term complications.

Challenges: Limited training on skin NTDs and often lacks access to updated diagnostic tools. Connectivity in her region is inconsistent.

What she seeks: A simple, culturally adapted mobile tool that empowers her to identify and refer cases confidently, even offline.

Gebre

Age: 46

Location: Tigray region, Ethiopia

Background: Regional health officer overseeing public health interventions. Collaborates with international partners on infectious disease control.

Motivations: Aims to reduce skin NTD burden through better surveillance and early treatment pathways.

Challenges: Gaps in consistent case reporting, lack of centralized data on skin NTD prevalence.

What he seeks: A reliable system that supports real-time data collection and helps map disease hotspots for better resource allocation.

Joy

Age: 52

Location: Enugu, Nigeria

Background: Senior consultant dermatologist at a teaching hospital. Trains young doctors and contributes to national health policy.

Motivations: Committed to advancing dermatological education and ensuring equitable access to diagnostic resources.

Challenges: Overwhelmed by demand; limited AI integration in current clinical workflows.

What she seeks: Evidence-based tools that augment training, build datasets, and support inclusive healthcare innovations.

Personality

Archetypes

Narrative archetypes allow SkincAir to resonate emotionally and culturally with a diverse group of users. Rooted in purpose, these archetypes guide how the brand communicates, builds trust, and drives meaningful innovation—especially in sensitive healthcare contexts.

The Caregiver

Core trait: Empathy

Role: Supports and uplifts health workers serving vulnerable communities

Brand voice: Reassuring, people-first, collaborative

Purpose: To care for those who care for others, offering tools that save time, increase precision, and reduce diagnostic inequality.

The Sage

Core trait: Wisdom

Role: Translates complex AI into understandable, usable solutions

Brand voice: Calm, knowledgeable, evidence-based

Purpose: To build trust through accuracy, transparency, and open science.

Tone of voice

Supportive and Respectful

Address all users—especially field workers and underserved populations—with empathy and care.

Pragmatic and Informed

Communicate in a grounded tone, backed by science and public health priorities.

Collaborative and Inclusive

Reflect co-creation, community feedback, and cultural sensitivity in every message.

Hopeful and Mission-Driven

Emphasize how scalable digital tools can reduce disease and improve lives now—not just in the future.

Don't say

AI that solves Africa's skin disease crisis.

Center frontline expertise and partnership.

Finally, a tool that replaces traditional diagnosis.

Emphasize enhancement and integration.

This app fixes poor healthcare in remote areas.

Highlight co-creation and agency.

We built the largest NTD database to lead the fight.

Replace ownership claims with collective, inclusive narratives.

Smart scanning will eliminate diagnostic errors.

Don't overpromise; use careful, ethical framing.

Do say

AI that supports early detection of skin NTDs with local health workers.

A digital companion that strengthens field diagnosis through AI.

Designed with and for communities to improve access to skin health services.

Together, we're building an open-access skin NTD database to advance care.

AI-assisted tools help improve diagnostic confidence and consistency.

Visual Tools

Logo

TREE

HANDS

Mark construction

FINAL CONCEPT

Logo

Wordmark

SkincAlr

The logotype must follow this actual order of capital letters.

A 1-colour solution is acceptable in a monochromatic version

or possibly in a 2-colour solution with **AI** highlighted.

Logo

Setup vertical

SkincAlr

Logo

setup horizontal

Logo

Main version

Logo

SkincAlr

Alternate version

SkincAlr

Logo

SkincAlr

Monochromatic version

SkincAlr

Logo

Main version

Logo

Alternate version

Logo

Monochromatic version

DO's

DON'Ts

Logo

DO's and DON'Ts

The safety distance of the single mark is obtained by placing half of the thumb horizontally between the widest part of the right thumb of the mark and the very beginning of the logotype, for the horizontal version.

Using the same criteria for the distance between the brand and the logotype, we can derive the safety margins of the logo. It is sufficient to multiply by 2 the length between the pictogram and the logotype.

The vertical version of the logo needs a distance of half a thumb between the bottom of the mark and the apex of the small letters, i.e. i, n, r.

Horizontal

Vertical

Use monochromatic (white) version with colored or photography background

Use main logo version with white or light grey background

In a monochromatic light context, using the black version of the logo is the best choice

Logo

DO's and DON'Ts

always check the contrast
between logo and background

always check the logo
contrast on photographs

do NOT change the logo opacity

do NOT recolor the logo

do NOT outline the logo

do NOT stretch the logo or apply any effect

Colors

Introduction to the selected color palette for a brand. The brand's color scheme includes the primary, secondary, accent (or exception to use in case of an error), and neutral colors such as white or black.

The primary colors are the most dominant and recognizable color of the brand, followed by the secondary colors that complement and contrast with the primary color.

The secondary colors are ordered according to the priority indicated in the diagram on the right, where the top color has higher priority than the bottom color.

Refer to the diagram on the right for specific colors and their contrast ratio*

*Source: www.w3.org/TR/WCAG20/#visual-audio-contrast

Colors

Gradient table

100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%
80%	80%	80%	80%	80%	80%	80%
60%	60%	60%	60%	60%	60%	60%
40%	40%	40%	40%	40%	40%	40%
20%	20%	20%	20%	20%	20%	20%

Specification of the gradient table

The gradient table indicates which neutral color (black or white) to use for writing text based on the percentage of opacity. Refer to the adjacent table for more information.

Typography

Titles

The font displayed is intended for use only in titles and subtitles.

DOWNLOAD FONT <https://fonts.google.com/specimen/Livvic>

Aa

Titles

Livvic **Bold**

Aa Bb Cc Dd Ee Ff Gg Hh Ii

Jj Kk Ll Mm Nn Oo Pp Qq

Rr Ss Tt Uu Vv Ww Xx Yy Zz

0123456789

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Typography

Body

The font displayed is intended for use only in titles and subtitles.

DOWNLOAD FONT <https://fonts.google.com/specimen/Host+Grotesk>

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Host Grotesk

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Vv Ww Xx Yy Zz

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Mockups

SkincAir

Title example

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Title example

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Title example

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